

The News Treatment in the Local Satellite Channels of the Issue of Demonstrations in Iraq, an Analytical Study

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Abstract

Our research seeks to identify the frameworks for the news treatment of the issue of demonstrations on Iraqi satellite channels, and according to a survey conducted by the researcher on a sample of the general public, three channels were chosen represented by Al-Iraqiya and Tigris Al-Ahd, the first expressing the government viewpoint, then a semi-official channel, and the second expressing the point of view. The secular partisan view and the third represent the Islamic partisan point of view, with a research problem formulated with the following question: What frameworks for news treatment of the issue of demonstrations in the Iraqi channels in question? Main news at eight in the evening, where 28 news bulletins were selected for each channel by the method of regular random sampling, bringing the total of the bulletins subject to analysis to 84 bulletins, using a content analysis form as a tool to collect data, in order to achieve the objectives of the research in identifying the frameworks for the news treatment of the issue of demonstrations in the channels The three, and the active forces that adopted it, in addition to the key words that it provided in its handling of the issue, and the research reached a realization. The "frameworks of solutions" ranked first in the Iraqi and Al-Ahed channels, and then "the frameworks of conflict and "humanitarian concerns" ranked second and third, while "the frameworks of human concerns" came first in the Tigris channel, and then "frameworks of conflict" and "solutions" in the two ranks. The second and third, Al-Iraqiya TV shed light on "the religious authority, Sayyid Ali al-Sistani" as an effective force in the first place and then the "United Nations Organization" in the second degree. The United States of America and the United Nations were ranked second and third respectively, while tigris TV focused on "civilian activists" as an effective force in the first place, and then "the religious authority, Mr. Ali al-Sistani," and the "United Nations Organization" in the second and third ranks respectively. The words "burning" and "sabotage" were mentioned in the Iraqi and Tigris channels primarily among the pivotal words, while the word "Joker" appeared in the Al-Ahed channel in the first place, followed by the words "burning" and "sabotage" in the second place.

Introduction

Iraqi satellite channels differ in the way they deal with important events according to their reference, ownership and funding sources, especially local events that affect the interests of the public on one side and the interests of the political parties that run satellite channels on the other hand, as this is reflected in the news contents of these channels according to a concept called editorial policy In its orbit, news content production processes, which vary from channel to channel, despite dealing with the same issues, take place as a result of reformulating information about events, arranging them and presenting them in a specific way as part of a process called news processing, during which certain aspects of the events are neglected, and focus on aspects Other, and crystallized it in a unified idea that is presented to the audience in a specific context that gives it the meaning that the channel wants to convey to the audience, these stages that the news content-making process goes through until it reaches the recipient, is carried out according to a theory called the news framing theory, meaning that the treatment and framing represent two processes. One of them complements the other in producing news contents on television channels with the aim of influencing audience attitudes about the issues they cover.

Methodological framework for research

First: the research problem

The research problem in this study revolves around the frameworks for the news treatment of the issue of demonstrations in the Al-Iraqiya, Tigris and Al-Ahd channels, because these three channels represent the

importance of the Iraqi society, as they appeared as the three channels most watched by the public according to an exploratory study conducted by the researcher on a sample of the general public. The research problem is the following question: "What are the frameworks for the news treatment of the demonstrations issue on Iraqi satellite channels?"

This question is divided into a group of sub-questions, which we express as follows:

- 1- What are the frameworks for the news treatment of the demonstrations issue in the Iraqi satellite broadcasts in question?
- 2- What are the active forces adopted by the three channels in question in their news treatment of the demonstrations issue?
- 3- What are the central words mentioned by the three channels in their news treatment of the demonstrations issue?

Second: The importance of research

When talking about the importance of the research, it is necessary to address two aspects: The first: the scientific importance: as this research is of scientific importance, as it is one of the few studies that dealt with the issue of demonstrations in the Al-Iraqiya, Tigris and Al-Ahed channels, in a study aimed at analyzing the content of the news bulletins of these channels, and the second: Societal importance: as this research is prepared with the frameworks it monitors for the news treatment of the issue of demonstrations in the Iraqi channels in question, it is directed towards society in order to know the way in which these channels deal in dealing with important local issues that affect the lives of individuals, which can reveal many things Which society is ignorant of about the work of Iraqi satellite channels and helps it to distinguish between real information and fake or manipulated information.

Third: Research objectives

The research seeks to achieve three objectives, which are as follows:

- 1- Getting acquainted with the frameworks for the news treatment of the demonstrations issue in the Iraqi satellite broadcasts in question.
- 2- Knowing the active forces adopted by the three channels in question in their news treatment of the demonstrations issue.
- 3- Disclosure of the pivotal words mentioned by the three channels in their news treatment of the demonstrations issue.

Fourth: Research methodology and type

This research used the descriptive explanatory survey method for the content represented by news bulletins on the Iraqi satellite channels in question, analyzing them and extracting the frameworks that were used in addressing the issue of demonstrations, but in terms of type, this research is classified into descriptive research, because it seeks to provide all information about the phenomenon in the channels. The Iraqi satellite channel in question, knowing that the researcher will conduct a systematic comparison with results between the three channels in the analytical study.

Sixth: Research areas

The specified date range was from (October 1, 2019) to (December 31, 2019).

Seventh: The Research Association

The research community is determined through the Iraqi satellite channels that had a role in addressing the issue of the demonstrations, and since the Iraqi media space includes many channels with different orientations and references, the researcher divided these channels into three sections, which are semi-official channels, secular party channels, and party channels. Islamic channels, the location, and the selection on Iraqi channels, as the research targets a local issue that Iraqi channels are mainly concerned with, more than any other type of channel, whether Arab or directed. In Arabic, according to the scientific observation of the researcher.

Eighth: The research sample

The research sample was determined by three channels that appeared after conducting an exploratory study on a sample of the people of Baghdad governorate, namely the Al-Iraqiya, Tigris and Al-Ahed channels, according to a division adopted by the researcher that included three types of Iraqi channels, which are semi-official channels, secular party channels, and Islamic party channels. With the exception of the Kurdistan Region channels that speak Arabic and Kurdish.

Ninth: Research tools

The researcher used two tools to collect the data and information necessary to achieve the research objectives, namely:

First: Scientific observation: The researcher used this tool in general in all stages of the research, starting with identifying the research topic, developing his methodological plan, building his theoretical framework and ending with writing the results, especially in conducting the research. Analytical study of the news releases of the three concerned channels.

Second: The content analysis model: The researcher used this tool in analyzing the news releases of the three concerned channels, to find out the frameworks for the news treatment of the issue of demonstrations in these channels during the period specified in the research sample.

Tenth: honesty and stability

1- Honesty: The researcher relied on apparent honesty, which refers to submitting the content analysis model to a group of expert referees in the field of media and psychology ([*]), in order to express their opinions and observations on the most important and sub-categories that make up the content analysis model, To demonstrate its safety, clarity, interconnectedness, and ability to access data and information that achieve the research objectives.

2. Reliability: The researcher used the method of re-testing with the same service as content analysis again from another researcher ([*]) and after applying the Hoselti equation, it was found that the difference between the two analyzes was small, as the stability ratio reached (0.95) after analyzing the proportion (10%) of the sample.

Eleventh: Defining concepts and terminology

- 1- Processing news: the process of selecting and reformulating the events included in the issue of the demonstrations, and presenting them in line with the editorial policy of the media institution, and in a way that reflects the viewpoint of the political party that controls it or its financing.
- 2- The subject of the demonstrations: These are the demonstrations that began on October 1, 2019 in Baghdad and the governorates of central and southern Iraq, and the political, security, military, legal and humanitarian events that followed, and the internal, external and international events that followed. Positions taken against them.
- 3- Iraqi satellite channels: Iraqi satellite channels that dealt with the demonstrations through their news bulletins.

The second - twelve: previous studies

1- (Study of Hussein Nasser Hussein 2007) (Hussein 2007).

This study aimed to identify the nature of the news treatment of the Iraqi issue on BBC television, and the topics that focused on covering the news of this topic and the trends that were addressed, and this study was classified within descriptive studies, and the poll method was used in analyzing the content of the news bulletins of the aforementioned channel, while a tool Analysis to form a secure dataset in it.

2- (Study of Ismail Alwan Obaid 2009) (Obaid 2009).

This study aimed to identify the priorities of news ranking in Iraqi satellite channels' bulletins within the framework of the value news adopted by the organizers of Al-Baghdadi's bulletin, and the type of news treatment that was carried out on. News Bulletin (Today by Hour) It is the study of descriptive studies that used the survey method to analyze the content of the newsletter on the Al-Baghdadiya channel and the questionnaire in it was a tool for collecting data. .

2- (The study of Heba Shaheen 2013) (Shaheen 2013).

This study aims to reveal how the free Arab and Egyptian election channels are addressed in terms of form and content, and to monitor aspects of agreement and differences between the two channels with regard to frameworks for news coverage of the elections, and this study belongs to descriptive studies, where it used the survey method, descriptive and deductive, as well as the comparative approach While the content analysis form was adopted as a tool for data collection.

Theoretical flew

First: the concept of news treatment

News processing is defined as the decisions that a caller makes regarding the manner in which he will present the code and the content. He may choose a specific information and ignore another, and repeat the evidence in which his opinion is proven, and he may summarize what he says at the beginning or the end (Rashti, 1987, p.152). It is also known as the media framing process imposed by the institution's policy in dealing with events and issues in reporting news and how it is presented here. This process includes explanatory additions or the practice of monitoring and analysis. And manipulating words or interfering with the evaluation of information in the soul, but even expressing an opinion and presenting proposals and solutions (Kashkool, 2020), and there are those who describe news processing as a process that includes choosing the information that will be used as news material and verifying its sources and re-editing it according to many criteria, the most important of which is the news policy. Of the media organization, its professional and ethical considerations, the subjective and objective aspirations of the callers, and the nature. From the atmosphere of communication, the limits of freedoms in dealing with sensitive issues, the professionalism of the media owners, the style in which news is formulated, and the choice of headlines and location. The same applies to the structure and delivery of news (Al-Ani, 2012, pp. 134-135). This is why news text is described as the product of a series of cognitive and social processes, which are reflected in a series of basic contexts involved in the making and circulation of news.

According to the concept of processing, the news material goes through multiple stages, during which certain decisions are made regarding whether this material will remain as it is, or after some changes have been introduced, and among these decisions are the intentional deletion or failure to delete the transmission of some

news, information, opinions and criticism. And display. Bad behavior and protection of the confidentiality of information sources, in addition to the values that should be emphasized, and the values that are unwanted or required to be addressed (Muhammad, 2014, pages 92-93).

According to the previous data, we can define news processing as "the process of reprocessing, starting with the event of selecting the stage, then selecting the information it contains, formulating the system, conveying the required meaning and placing it. For them in the context it gives it an imaginary desire for a media organization to present its cards, and to achieve the goals that E. of her guardian seeks to achieve." And E. The desired effect occurs to the audience. "

Second: the concept of framing

Despite the increasing interest of researchers in the framing approach and the amount of studies that have dealt with this concept, no agreed set of basic assumptions regarding framing of the research has been reached due to the ambiguity surrounding the concept and the term framing itself (Carpentier) (2010, p.97) where there is confusion in the field of Media studies on the basis of the researchers' disagreement with the use of a unified scientific term to denote framing, there are three explicit terms that denote it, namely: framing, which refers to the framing process as a general multi-party communication process, and the term frameworks that refers to the angles and aspects through which it takes place. Covering different events, topics, personalities, and issues and their impacts on the public, while the third is a framework term that refers to a "framework" and does not precisely express what is meant by the framing process (Hassouna, 2015). ng, as Goffman defines it from a sociological perspective, is a classification method that allows its users to identify, visualize, diagnose and classify everyday incidents (Goffman.E. 21). For media, framing is defined as the conceptual tools that individuals and the media rely on to convey, interpret and evaluate information (Gorp (2007, p.62), where framing provides a specific context for understanding communication by including specific topics and focusing on them (Lynam (2016, 2016)). 63) The framework is the central idea around which news content is organized and that would provide the appropriate context to determine the nature of the issue through the use of selection and confirmation methods (Al-Debaisi, 2017, p.84). Prominence in the communication message in order to reinforce a specific definition, causal explanation, ethical evaluation, or recommendation to address a problem (M. Entman, 1993, p. 52) Frameworks serve to make some ideas more prominent in the news text, others less obvious, and other ideas not. Fully Visible (RM) The idea of placing the f screening work depends on selecting some information related to the topic and making it clearer, meaningful and more likely to be remembered by the audience (Al-Sayed, 2006, p. 200) as the idea of framing is based on choosing some information related to the topic and increasing the likelihood of He is remembered by the audience (El-Sayed, 2006, p. 200), through keywords, symbols, and concepts. And metaphorical description and visual images that were made. Shaping it, focusing on it, highlighting it in the story of the news, and repeating it to reinforce specific ideas, words and images, excluding other ideas, or making special recommendations from the contact point (Al-Hadi, 2014, p.14).).

Second: framing mechanisms

Framing mechanisms are the methods used by callers and their institutions in reformulating various events and issues within a specific framework, and there are three main mechanisms used in developing media frameworks, which are (Al-Shujairi, 2018, pages 353-354). :

- 1- Goodwill: This mechanism is used to highlight specific events within the issue at hand, or to highlight specific information within the event so that it can be observed, and given meaning to facilitate its memory by recipients.
- 2- Selection: It is a selection process according to professional, subjective, institutional and cultural criteria by the person in charge of the communication or the media when covering an event or issue by focusing on certain aspects and angles.
- 3- Exclusion or omission: This is done by means of a financial that ignores the issues of certain or specific events within a case or ignores certain information within what happened. Usually, three basic concepts are associated with this mechanism, which are objectivity, ideology and gatekeeping.

E practically flew

First: the sub-categories of the main frameworks

1: Frame solutions

Table No. (1) Shows frameworks for solutions in the news treatment of the demonstrations issue in the relevant channels

Total		the covenant		Tigris		Iraqi		Frame solutions
%	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	
%16.5	45	%13.1	17	%15	9	%23.2	19	1. Amending the election law
%15.1	41	%15.4	20	%20	12	%10.2	9	2. The choice of prime minister is uncontroversial
%14.7	40	%15.4	20	%15	9	%13.6	11	3. Meet the demands of the

								demonstrators
%14.4	39	%15.4	20	%5	3	%19.6	16	4. Legislative reforms
%9.2	25	%11.5	15th	%0	0	%12.2	10	5. Amend the constitution
%7.7	21	%4.6	6	%16.7	10	%6.3	5	6. Dismissal of Abdul Mahdi's government
%4.8	13	%3.9	5	%8.3	5	%3.7	3	7. Making ministerial reshuffles
%4.4	12	%4.6	6	%6.7	4	%2.6	2	8. Reforming the political system
%3.7	10	%0.7	1	%8.3	5	%4.9	4	9. Carrying out government reforms
%3.3	9	%3.1	4	%3.3	2	%3.7	3	10. Hold early elections
%3.3	9	%6.9	9	%0	0	%0	0	11. Retaining Adel Abdul Mahdi
%2.9	8	%5.4	7	%1.7	1	%0	0	12. Provincial councils dissolution
%100	272	%100	130	%100	60	%100	82	Total

The results of the above table and your escalating solutions are as follows: The first prize category was replaced by the "amended election law" with a percentage (16.5%), followed by the second place category "selecting a controversial prime minister" at a rate of (15.1%), and in the third place came the category of "meeting Demonstrators' demands by (14.7%), and the fourth category of "legislative reforms" at a rate of (14.4%). As for the group, the "amendment of the constitution" category came in fifth place with (9.2%), then the "dismissal of Abdul Mahdi's government" ranked sixth with (9.2%) 7.7%), and ranked seventh. The category for "making ministerial reforms" came to a percentage (4.8%), followed by the "reforming the political system" category with a percentage (4.4%), and the category for "contracting government reforms" ranked ninth. From (3.7%), the categories of "early elections" and "retaining the conservatives", "Adel Abdul Mahdi" came in the tenth place (3.3%), while the dissolved category "dissolving provincial councils" "B" came last with a rate of (2.9%). We notice from the above table that there is a variation between the three channels in the extent of interest in the subcategories. Frameworks solutions during its news treatment of the issue of demonstrations, which sometimes reach total exclusion, indicating that the three channels follow the mechanisms of prominence and exclusion within the theory of news frameworks.

2: Frameworks of Conflict

Table No. (2) Clarifies the frameworks of the conflict in dealing with the news about the issue of demonstrations in the relevant channels

Total		the covenant		Tigris		Iraqi		Frames conflict
%	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	
%25.9	63	%17.1	20	%40.2	35	%20.5	8	1. Political differences over choosing a new prime minister
%14.8	36	%5.1	6	%24.2	21	%23	9	2. The momentum of the demonstrations continued
%12.8	31	%22.2	26	%3.5	3	%5.2	2	3. Political disputes over reforms
%11.9	29	%17.1	20	%0	0	%23	9	4. Riots occur
%11.9	29	%12.8	15	%6.9	6	%20.5	8	5. Escalation by closing institutions and blocking roads
%7.5	18	%12.8	15	%3.5	3	%0	0	6. Take strict security measures
%7	17	%1.7	2	%17.2	15	%0	0	7. Use of violence against protesters
%4.1	10	%6.8	8	%0	0	%5.2	2	8. Burning work occurs
%4.1	10	%4.3	5	%4.6	4	%2.6	1	9. Always strike and open sit-ins
%100	243	%100	117	%100	87	%100	39	Total

The results of the above table show that the frameworks for conflict in the three channels came as follows: In the first place, the category of "political differences over choosing a new prime minister" came with a percentage of (25.9%), then the category of "continuous momentum of demonstrations" B came in second place with a percentage of (14.8%). Followed by the "political differences over reforms" category, ranking third, with a rate of 12.8%, and fourth. "Riots" and "escalating the closure of institutions and roadblocks" were at a rate (11.9%), and in the fifth place the category of "taking strict security measures" was replaced by (7.5%), then came (7.5%). The "use of violence against demonstrators" category B came in sixth place (7%), while the categories "incidence of arson attacks" and "permanent strikes and open sit-ins" ranked last, at a rate of (4.1%) despite tyranny in light of the disagreement about The subject of demonstrations in most of their events,

its frameworks came second after frameworks for solutions, due to the interest of the concerned channels, especially the Iraqi channel and Al-Ahed channel, in trying to calm the situation and focus on solutions that will achieve this goal, and the fact that the conflict is one of the most prominent features of the demonstrations issue, so the option to exclude its events are very difficult, but its priority was possible to control it during the news to address the issue in the three channels concerned, and this explains why it won the second place, as for the sub-groups, the political conflict had the largest share among the other groups.

3: Framing human interest

Table No. (3) Clarifies the frameworks for humanitarian concerns in dealing with the news about the issue of the demonstrations in the relevant channels

Total		the covenant		Tigris		Iraqi		Frame human fears
%	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	
27.3	45	%19.5	9	%32.3	31	%21.9	5	1- Condemning the use of violence against demonstrators and calling for their protection
18.2	30	%8.7	4	%24	23	%13	3	2- Martyrs and wounded protesters
13.9	23	%8.7	4	%17.7	17	%8.7	2	3- Supporting the demonstrators and showing solidarity with their demands
12.1	20	%13	6	%8.3	8	%26.2	6	4- Social events in the demonstration squares
7.3	12	%23.9	11	%0	0	%4.3	1	5- Civilian martyrs and wounded.
6.7	11	%0	0	%10.5	10	%4.3	1	6- Arrest and kidnapping of demonstrations perpetrators
5.5	9	%13	6	%2	2	%4.3	1	7- Exploitation of school students in demonstrations
4.2	7	%2.2	1	%5.2	5	%4.3	1	8- The funeral of the martyrs in the demonstration squares
3	5	%4.5	2	%0	0	%13	3	9- Victims (martyrs and wounded) among the security forces
1.8	3	%6.5	3	%0	0	%0	0	10- Condemning the crime of Al-Wathba
% 100	165	%100	46	%100	96	%100	23	Total

The results of the above table regarding frameworks for humanitarian concerns show that its sub-categories came as follows: "Condemning the use of violence against demonstrators and calling for their protection" came in first with a percentage (27.3%), and in second place came the "victims (martyrs and wounded)" category among the demonstrators. B by (18.2%), and in the third place came the category "Supporting the Demonstrators and Solidarity with their Demands." With a percentage of (13.9%), while it came fourth in the "Social Events in the Square to Prove B" category with (12.1%), and the "Victims" category was replaced. (Killed and wounded) among civilians "to fifth place (7.3%). The category of "arresting and kidnapping of figures active in demonstrations "came in sixth place with a percentage (6.7%), and in seventh place came the category of " school exploitation. " Students in a demonstration came in category B with a rate of (5.5%), followed by "the funeral of the martyrs in the demonstration squares" in eighth place with (4.2%), and in the ninth place came the "victims (martyrs and wounded). B percentage (3%), and finally the category "crime scene condemnation" was replaced by (1.8%), and humanitarian concerns in the issue of demonstrations represent an important focus as a result. Events witnessed by protesters and security forces, as well as civilians, were subjected to acts of violence that led to the occurrence of Martyrs and wounded, and the political, human rights and international stances that followed, and this explains their ranking third among the overall results in processing the news for the three channels concerned, and since each channel has a news policy that deals with the subject according to it, we notice that there are differences between the amount of interest for each group.

4: Framing the results

Table No. (4) Shows the results frameworks for news channels 'treatment of the subject of the demonstrations in question

Total		the covenant		Tigris		Iraqi		Frame the results
%	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	
43.9	65	%40.3	23	%65	26	%31.4	16	1- Opening and investigating corruption files
8.1	12	%10.5	6	%12.5	5	%1.9	1	2- The resignation of government officials and members of Parliament

8.1	12	%8.8	5	%0	0	%13.8	7	3- Attracting graduates
6.1	9	%7	4	%12.5	5	%0	0	4- The resignation of Prime Minister Adel Abdul Mahdi
6.1	9	%15.8	9	%0	0	%0	0	5- Lack of security conditions
5.4	8	%5.3	3	%0	0	%9.8	5	6- Supporting needy families
5.4	8	%1.7	1	%0	0	%13.7	7	7- Financial losses for store owners
4.1	6	%5.3	3	%0	0	%5.9	3	8- Destruction of public and private property
3.4	5	%0	0	%2.5	1	%7.9	4	9- Forming committees to implement the demands of the demonstrators
3.4	5	%0	0	%0	0	%9.8	5	10- Providing jobs
2.7	4	%5.3	3	%0	0	%1.9	1	11- Disrupt public life
2	3	%0	0	%7.5	3	%0	0	12- Iraq lost its membership in the Human Rights Council
1.3	2	%0	0	%0	0	%3.9	2	13- Terminate their contracts
% 100	148	%100	57	%100	40	%100	51	Total

The disclosure of the results of the above table of the results of frameworks that focused on the three concerned channels during the discussion of the issue of the demonstrations came as follows: In the first place, the category of "opening corruption files and investigations" was replaced by percentages. From (43.9%) T fulfilled the "resignation of government officials and members of Parliament" and the "appointment of graduates" to the second place with a percentage of (8.1) either of the two categories, "the resignation of Prime Minister Adel Abdul-Mahdi" and the "security conditions beyond control" of the center The third with a percentage (6.1%), and in the fourth place came the "physical losses of shopkeepers" by (5.4%), and the "physical losses of shop owners" by (5.4%). - The destruction of public and private property "in the fifth rank (4.1%), followed by the two categories of "forming committees to implement the demands of the demonstrators." And "job creation" ranked sixth with a percentage (3.4%), and it came in seventh place replacing the "public life disabled" category with (2.7%), then that category "with the loss of Iraq's membership in the Human Rights Council" ranked eighth with (2%), and finally the category of "re-disclosed" was replaced by (1.3%). The data in this table reflect the results that were achieved against the background of demonstrations, whether negative or positive, political, economic or security ... etc., and according to the treatment of the three news channels concerned, it has Some results received remarkable attention, others appeared to be less important, and some were excluded.

5: Education frameworks

Table No. (5) Shows the educational frameworks in the news channels' treatment of the demonstrations under discussion

Total		the covenant		Tigris		Iraqi		Education frameworks
%	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	
28.5	29	%24.6	16	%33.3	6	%37	7	1- Maintaining peaceful demonstrations
14.8	15th	%13.9	9	%33.3	6	%0	0	2- Warning against exploiting demonstrations
12.7	13	%16.9	11	%0	0	%10.5	2	3- Urging the rejection of the strike behavior once and for all
12.7	13	%20	13	%0	0	%0	0	4- He denied the validity of the inaccurate reports about the demonstrations
8.8	9	%4.6	3	%22.4	4	%10.5	2	5- Artistic, literary and social events in the demonstration squares
4.9	5	%3.1	2	%5.5	1	%10.5	2	6- Staying in places designated for demonstration
4.9	5	%4.6	3	%0	0	%10.5	2	7- Staying away from ports, ports and vital centers
4.9	5	%7.7	5	%0	0	%0	0	8- Detecting and distinguishing saboteurs
3.9	4	%1.5	1	%5.5	1	%10.5	2	9- Preserving public and private property
3.9	4	%3.1	2	%0	0	%10.5	2	10- Not to offend the security forces
% 100	102	%100	65	%100	18	%100	19	Total

The results of the above table were revealed for the education frameworks adopted by the three concerned channels by addressing the issue of the demonstrations, and they were as follows: where the category "maintaining peaceful demonstrations" ranked first with a rate (28.5%), followed by the second place in the category "warning the exploitation of demonstrations" by (14.8%), and in the third place came the categories of

“Urging to reject strike behavior permanently” and “Denying inaccurate news about the strike movement”. Demonstrations "by (12.7%), then the category of" artistic and social activities in the squares to prove "ranked fourth with a percentage (8.8%), and the data came in fifth place" to stay in the dedicated display. As for places, “Staying away from ports, vital centers and ports,” and “Detecting and distinguishing saboteurs,” the percentage was (4.9%), while it reached the categories “Preserving private public property” and “Doing no harm to security.” The orces came in last place with a percentage of (3.9%). The categories of this table revolve around raising the demonstrators' awareness of unwanted practices, warning against exploiting demonstrations, and revealing inaccurate news about them. To reinforce imaginative behavior, the results of the channel's news processing show a mixed interest in subcategories of education frameworks.

6: Frameworks of Liability Ratios

Table No. (6) Clarifies the frameworks for attributing responsibility in treating news channels to the cause of the demonstrations in question.

Total		the covenant		Tigris		Iraqi		Frame liability ratios
%	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	
29	18	%32.2	18	%0	0	%0	0	1- Holding the President of the Republic responsible for obstructing the selection of the Prime Minister
27.4	17	%30.3	17	%0	0	%0	0	2- Holding America responsible for violence and managing acts of sabotage and sedition
27.4	17	%25	14	%0	0	%100	3	3- Holding external and internal parties responsible for creating chaos and fueling the street
8.1	5	%8.9	5	%0	0	%0	0	4- Holding the electronic armies responsible for the escalation in the demonstrations
4.9	3	%0	0	%100	3	%0	0	5- Hold the government responsible for killing demonstrators and assaulting them
3.2	2	%3.6	2	%0	0	%0	0	6- Holding the Ba'ath Party responsible for fueling the situation
% 100	62	%100	56	%100	3	%100	3	Total

The results of the above table illustrate the frameworks of attribution of responsibility in dealing with the news of the issue of demonstrations in the three channels, and they were represented as follows: Firstly, the category “Holding the President of the Republic responsible for obstructing the selection. From the Prime Minister” by (29%), and in the second place came the category “C. Holding America responsible for violence and managing acts of sabotage and stirring up strife" and "holding external and internal parties responsible for stirring up chaos and fueling the street" at a rate (27.4%), and in third place came the category of "holding electronic armies responsible for the escalation in demonstrations" by (8.1%). The government attributed responsibility for the killings and attacks on demonstrators to the fourth place with a percentage (4.9%), while the dissolved group was dissolved. The category of "holding the Baath Party responsible for fueling the situation" ranked last (3.2%). The results of the classifications reveal this table on assigning responsibility for some of the events that occurred during the period of the demonstrations. For certain parties, some of them were named by their explicit names, and others were limited to an unspecified generalization, but it is striking that Al-Ahed channel was very interested in this category compared to the Iraqi and Tigris channels.

7: Legal frameworks

Table No. (7) Shows the legal frameworks in dealing with the news about the issue of demonstrations in the relevant channels

Total		the covenant		Tigris		Iraqi		Legal frameworks
%	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	
64.2	63	%53.2	25	%88.5	23	%60	15	1- Investigation into the events of the demonstrations
17.4	17	%19.3	9	%7.7	2	%24	6	2- Accountability for those outside the boundaries of peaceful protest
12.2	12	%23.3	11	%0	0	%4	1	3- Investigation into incidents of killing citizens during demonstrations
3.1	3	%2.1	1	%3.8	1	%4	1	4- Refusal to interfere in Iraqi affairs
3.1	3	%2.1	1	%0	0	%8	2	5- Commitment to the official working hours
100	98	%100	47	%100	26	%100	25	Total

Discloses the results of the table above the legal frameworks contained in the treatment of news for the cause of demonstrations in the three channels as follows: came the category of "investigating the events of

the demonstrations " B ranked first with a rate of (64.2% , (followed by the category of " accounting outlaws the limits of peaceful protest " In second place ,with a percentage of ,(17.4%) then the category of " Investigating incidents of killing citizens during the demonstrations " ranked third with a percentage of (12.2% , (and in fourth place came the categories of " Refusing to interfere in Iraqi affairs " and " Commitment to the official working hours " with a percentage of (3.1% , (and include these categories data legal - related issue demonstrations procedures , in terms of investigating the events that accompanied, such as acts of violence that led to the casualties of any party, and accounting breakers frameworks of peaceful demonstrations and other things other, and enjoyed This category is of different interest between the three channels under study ,as shown in the above results.

Second :the active powers

Table No7. It shows the forces active in the news treatment of the demonstrations issue in the channels in question

Total		the covenant		Tigris		Iraqi		Active forces
%	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	
37.7	205	%44.9	106	%19.9	43	%61.5	56	1- The religious authority, Mr. Ali al-Sistani
16	87	%11.4	27	%19.4	42	%19.8	18	2- The United Nations Organization
12.2	66	%6.3	15th	%22.2	48	%3.3	3	3- Civic activists
11.6	63	%15.7	37	%11.7	25	%1.1	1	4- United States of America
5.9	32	%4.7	11	%8.3	18	%3.3	3	5- The High Commission for Human Rights
3.9	21	%4.2	10	%3.2	7	%4.4	4	6- Iraqi Teachers Syndicate
3.9	21	%3.9	9	%3.7	8	%4.4	4	7- The sheikhs of the clan
3.3	18	%3	7	%4.2	9	%2.2	2	8- The leader of the Sadrist movement, Muqtada al-Sadr
2.7	15th	%2.1	5	%4.6	10	%0	0	9- Iran
1.5	8	%0.8	2	%2.8	6	%0	0	10- Foreign countries
1.3	7	%3	7	%0	0	%0	0	11- Arab countries
100	543	%100	236	%100	216	%100	91	Total

The results of the above table show the active forces that were mentioned in the news treatment of the demonstrations issue in the three channels in question , and they came as follows: In the first place, the category " Religious reference, Mr. Ali al-Sistani " came with a percentage of (37.7% , (followed by the " United Nations Organization " category . b second place with a rate of (16% , (and then the category of " civilian activists " ranked third with a rate of (12.2% , (this was the category of " the United States of America " ranked fourth with a rate of (11.6% , (followed by the category " Commission Higher human rights " ranked fifth with a rate of (5.9% , (and ranked sixth replaced the categories of " Iraqi teachers union " and " tribal leaders " b ratio of (3.9% , (and the category of " current leader of Sadr Muqtada al - Sadr " ,came the seventh rank with the proportion of of (3.3% , (either the category of " Iran " has got eighth place with a rate of (2.7% , (followed by the category of " foreign countries " ranked ninth with a rate of (1.5% , (while the last place was obtained by the category of " Arab countries " b ratio of (1.3% , (due to the different orientations of the three channels about the issue of demonstrations , we note that Al-Iraqiya and Al-Ahed channels have shown great interest in the religious reference, Ali al-Sistani as an effective force ,since the positions of these two channels are similar to many events related to the demonstrations, unlike the Tigris channel, which followed a different policy focused on supporting the demonstrators, so the results show that this channel showed greater interest to activists Civilians as an effective force more than any other group.

Third :Subcategories of the axial words

Table No8. Shows the pivotal words in the treatment of news for the cause of demonstrations in the channels in question

Total		the covenant		Tigris		Iraqi		Pivotal words
%	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	
22.4	74	60.8	45	6.7	5	32.5	24	1. burn
20.5	68	66.1	45	7.4	5	26.5	18	2. sabotage
20.5	68	97.1	66	2.9	2	0	0	3. the Joker
13.3	44	68.2	30	9.1	4	22.7	10	4. Infiltrators
13	43	67.4	29	4.7	2	27.9	12	5. Vandals
10.3	34	88.2	30	11.8	4	0	0	6. Temptation
100	331	74.1	245	6.6	22	19.3	64	Total

The results of the previous table reveal the pivotal words that appeared in the news treatment of the issue of the demonstrations in the channels under discussion, and came as follows: The word combustion ranked first with a percentage (22.4%), followed by the words T sabotage and the Joker in second place by (22.4%). 20.5%), then the word "sedition B" came in third place with a percentage (13.3%), and the word "sabotaged" ranked fourth with a percentage (13%), while the word "sedition B" came in the last place with a percentage (10.3). It is noticed from the results of the above table that the key words were generally mentioned in the Al-Ahed channel in the first place, where it recorded a percentage (74.1%), followed by Al-Iraqiya, a second category, at a rate of 19.3%, then the channel. Tigris finally rose by (6.6%) again, and the results show the phenomenon of roses. The pivotal words on Al-Ahed TV are more than the Tigris and Al-Iraqiya channels, and this reflects their focus on issues related to these words, especially the word Joker. Which is unique to describing saboteurs or infiltrators outside the frameworks of peaceful protest.

The most important results

1. The most prominent solutions focused on Al-Iraqiya and Al-Ahd channels focused on "amending the election law" and "undertaking legislative reforms," while Dijla TV focused on "choosing a non-controversial prime minister" and "removing the prime minister." The government of Adel Abdul Mahdi.
2. Al-Iraqiya TV sheds light on "riots" and "the continuing momentum of the demonstrations." Al-Ahed channel focused on "political differences over reforms" and "disagreements over choosing a new prime minister," while Tigris channel highlighted "political differences over choosing a new prime minister," "a new prime minister," and the "momentum of demonstrations" continued.
3. Al-Iraqiya TV focused primarily on "social activities in the demonstration squares" and "condemning the use of violence against demonstrators and calling for their protection." As for the channel, it shed light on "the occurrence of victims (martyrs and victims). The wounded) among civilians" and "condemning the use of violence against demonstrators and calling for their protection," while Dijla TV focused on "condemning the use of violence against demonstrators and calling for their protection" and "the occurrence of victims (martyrs). And wounded.) Among the demonstrators.
4. Al-Iraqiya TV focused in the results frameworks on "opening and investigating corruption files" and "material losses to shopkeepers", and Dijlah TV showed "opening and investigating corruption files" and "the resignation of Prime Minister Adel Abdul-Mahdi." As for Al-Ahed channel, it focused on "opening and investigating corruption files" and "insecurity in the security situation.
5. The three channels focused on educational frameworks on "preserving the peaceful demonstrations," and with the same concern, Dijla TV focused on "warning against exploiting demonstrations," while Al-Ahed channel shed light on "denying inaccurate news about the demonstrations Demonstrations.
6. The Iraqi and Tigris channels showed little interest in the issue of taking responsibility. As for Al-Ahd channel, it focused heavily on it, highlighting mainly "holding the president of the republic responsible for obstructing the choice of the prime minister" and "holding America responsible for violence and managing acts of sabotage and stirring up strife.
7. The three channels in the legal frameworks focused on investigating the events of the demonstrations in the first place, while the Iraqi and Al-Ahed channels focused on "holding those who violate the boundaries of peaceful protest accountable," and Al-Ahed channel. The third degree focused on "investigating incidents of killing citizens during demonstrations.
8. Al-Iraqia and Al-Ahd channels shed light on "the religious authority, Sayyid Ali al-Sistani" as an effective force in the first place, while Dijlah TV focused on "civilian activists" as an effective force in the first place.
9. The words "burning" and "sabotage" appeared on the Iraq and Tigris channels primarily among the pivotal words, while the word Joker appeared in the Al-Ahed channel in the first place, followed by the words "burning" and "sabotage" in the second place.

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